

Tunable light emission of Bi and V-doped borosilicate glasses for application in white light-emitting diodes

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ABSTRACT

Melt-quenched borosilicate glasses, co-doped with Bi and V ions, exhibited broad visible spectrum emissions. Bi ions primarily existed as Bi³⁺, acting as network modifiers, lowering the glass transition temperature linearly with increasing Bi content. V⁵⁺ ions adopted tetrahedral coordination as [VO₄]³⁻ units. Photoluminescence of Bi ions is shifted from blue to longer wavelengths with higher Bi content, associated with the stabilization of Bi²⁺ and the presence of Bi³⁺ in different local environments. Combined with V ions, the glasses emitted light covering the entire visible spectrum, offering the potential for white LED applications with correlated color temperatures ranging from 6135 to 4010 K. The highest QY was 11.9 and 8.0 % upon excitation at 325 and 340 nm.

1. Introduction

One of the major challenges of the future is the reduction in energy consumption and the energy consumed for general lighting accounts for over 15–20 % [1], therefore there is an urgent need to develop efficient light sources. Light-emitting diodes (LEDs) have a central role in the lighting market due to their many advantages as a fourth-generation solid-state lighting source [2,3]. LEDs are inexpensive and easy-to-install illumination devices with low energy consumption. Research based on phosphor-converted white light LEDs (pc-WLEDs) plays a central role worldwide. Many research projects are devoted to finding new light-emitting materials able to emit white light under UV excitation [4]. One of the most challenging aspects is to obtain white light from one phosphor that could be applied directly to commercially available LEDs. Commercially available WLEDs are based on blue InGaN LED with YAG:Ce³⁺ phosphor embedded in an organic resin [5–7]. Despite the good conversion efficiency of this yellow emitting phosphor, the organic resin has low thermal conductivity and poor thermal stability and may be damaged after long time usage or for high-power LEDs. This affects the efficiency of WLEDs and may also cause a shift of the emitted light with a consequent decrease in color rendering

[8–10]. Moreover, this pc-WLED suffers from low color rendering and one goal of artificial lighting is to make objects look natural – as they look under the sunlight [11].

Current processing routes to prepare new phosphors are based on solid-state reaction, solvothermal, and sol-gel methods. These methods provide efficient phosphors with increasing new crystalline phases as described in several review papers [12–14]. However, these materials need to be dispersed in a proper matrix to be used in pc-WLED and cannot be directly used in the powder form. Therefore, new strategies such as phosphor-in-glass materials have been widely studied [15].

Light emission in phosphors is generally obtained by adding a few amounts (mol%) of rare-earth ions (RE) to a dielectric. The combination of different RE ions has proved indeed to be an interesting way to fine tune the color of the emitted light [16–20]. Among the most promising RE ions for this doping procedure are Eu²⁺ and Ce³⁺ due to their broad-band emission and high intensity associated to their dipole-allowed transitions [21–23]. Moreover, they present strong UV absorption with no visible absorption bands, eliminating unwanted reabsorption processes. In spite that successful phosphors can be obtained by this method, there are economic and sustainability aspects regarding RE-dopants, such as the high price of RE ions due to

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purification processes to isolate individual compounds, as well as health concerns about their impact on humans that have been addressed by several international bodies and organizations including the European Union [24] and the United Nations [25]. Therefore, the quest for ions of alternative sustainable materials able to emit in a broad range has started.

Within this context, transition metals (TMs) as well as ions with ns^2 electronic configuration, such as bismuth, have gained increasing attention. In particular, Bi is a post-transition metal of the pnictogen group, that can take several oxidation states, and has proven to be useful for other photonic applications besides light emission, such as non-linear optical devices and plasmonic due to its unique dielectric function [26–28]. Up to date Bi-ion based light emission has been reported to span from blue to orange-red depending on the crystal field and oxidation state [29–33]. However, to our knowledge white light emission from Bi-doped materials has not been reported yet. So far, its typical blue emission (oxidation state +3) has to be combined with a yellow-orange emission from another ion to achieve white light emission. To this respect, it is very interesting to consider the emission from vanadium ions since it is very broad and intense [34], moreover, V is a relatively inexpensive and quite abundant element.

Although phosphors are usually crystalline, light-emitting glasses are very attractive inorganic luminescent materials due to their easiness of preparation and the possibility to shape them in thin films compatible with industrially available production methods for their integration in devices. An advantage of glasses is that they offer a huge variety of compositions because they are not constrained by stoichiometry. They have therefore demonstrated to be successful and efficient hosts for RE ions [35] and TMs [36]. In particular, borate and silicate glasses are transparent in the visible range and the combination of different glass formers opens the way to interesting new glass families with improved properties. Borosilicate glasses show an excellent combination of wide transmittance and good mechanical properties, and the addition of a borate network to a silica one increases the solubility of RE ions and TMs in the glass [37–40].

In this work, we propose and demonstrate the successful preparation of Bi and V co-doped borosilicate glass that shows broad photoluminescence emissions covering the full visible spectral range (400–700 nm) upon near UV. Moreover, we show how the spectral intensity distribution, i.e. the emitted color, can be changed by varying the Bi/V ratio and/or the excitation wavelength. Finally, it is interesting to note that the excitation wavelength of these glasses is compatible with that of commercial UV LEDs used for phosphor excitation. To the best of our knowledge, the white light emission in Bi and V co-doped glasses has not been reported before in the literature. In this work, we provide a thorough study of thermal, structural, compositional and optical properties of these glasses by using multiple techniques. This study opens a new route for the development of low-cost broadband emitting glasses for white light emission upon UV excitation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Design of glass composition and preparation

Glasses with composition (mol%) $35\text{SiO}_2\text{--}35\text{B}_2\text{O}_3\text{--}30\text{Na}_2\text{O--}x\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3\text{--}y\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ ($x = 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4$ and 6 ; $y = 0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.5) were prepared by the melt-quenching method. The precursor materials of B_2O_3 (99 + %), SiO_2 (99.5 %), Na_2CO_3 (99 %), Bi_2O_3 (99.9 %), and V_2O_5 (99.9 %) were weighted to prepare 6 g of batch, and the powders thoroughly mixed in an agate mortar for 15 min to ensure homogeneity. The batch composition was placed into a Pt crucible covered with a Pt lid and melted in air in an electric furnace at 1250°C for 2 h. Then the melt was poured onto a brass mold preheated at 250°C and annealed at 500°C for 2 h to remove internal stresses. Glass specimens with a thickness of 3 mm were polished for optical characterization. From now on, the glasses will be labeled as $x\text{Bi-}y\text{V}$ depending on their Bi_2O_3 and

V_2O_5 content.

The composition of the glasses was designed within the $\text{SiO}_2\text{--B}_2\text{O}_3\text{--Na}_2\text{O}$ system for simplicity and cost-effectiveness, and this system offers a broad glass-forming region. Moreover, the prepared composition gives the following properties: 1) transparency in the whole Vis range, 2) melting temperature $T < 1400^\circ\text{C}$, and 3) good solubility to doping ions (2–4 mol%) with limited concentration quenching. The amount of the glass network former was fixed to 70 % and for the modifier to 30 % to have a quite open glass network, moreover, 30 mol% of network modifier ensures a proper melting at temperatures lower than 1300°C . The use of Na_2O was preferred due to its lower price compared to Li_2O , and Na_2O reduces the glass viscosity better than K_2O . Moreover, higher amounts of modifier cations or the use of K_2O instead of Na_2O will shift the glass absorption edge towards a longer wavelength due to the higher polarizability of the electronic cloud. This will provoke a higher absorption of UV photons, thus removing more excitation photons.

The $\text{SiO}_2/\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio determined the absorption edge of the glass, the transparency range in the UV–Vis range and the melting temperature. Higher amounts of SiO_2 increase the viscosity of the melt, and silicate glasses are known to have good mechanical and chemical resistance but low solubility of RE and transition or post-transition metals [41–44]. On the other side, the addition of B_2O_3 increases the solubility of dopants but B_2O_3 also increases the phonon energy of the glass network. Therefore, the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio was fixed at 50/50. The idea to use melting temperature below $1300\text{--}1400^\circ\text{C}$ to prepare these glasses was related to: 1) reducing the energy consumption and 2) reducing the amount of Bi^0 that can precipitate during the melting. Some authors have described how Bi-doped glasses can become black due to Bi_2O_3 decomposition into metallic Bi^0 at high melting temperatures [45,46]. Therefore, we chose a melting temperature high enough to pour the melt as well as sufficiently low to keep the glass transparent.

2.2. Thermal, structural, and chemical characterization

Thermal characterization was performed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using an SDT Q600 (TA Instruments) thermogravimetric analyzer. 15–20 mg of powder samples were placed into a Pt crucible and the analysis was performed from 50 to 700°C at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Several techniques were used for structural and compositional/chemical characterization as described below.

The elemental composition of the glasses was performed by ICP-OES analysis. Glass powder samples were digested in a Berghof Speedwave 4 microwave digestion apparatus by reaction of aqua regia and hydrofluoric acid at the temperature of 200°C in a closed system. Elemental content determinations were performed using ICP OES 5100SVDV (Agilent) in axial and radial modes. The calibration curves are constructed using certified standards. The internal standard method was used to correct for non-spectral interferences. Scandium was used as the internal standard.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) of powder samples was measured by a Philips X'Pert MPD diffractometer in theta-2theta configuration. Diffractograms were acquired in the angular range of $10\text{--}90^\circ$ using a step size of 0.02° .

Fourier-transformed infrared spectra (FT-IR) were acquired with a Spectrum Two (PerkinElmer) spectrometer in the range $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} using the attenuated total reflection (ATR) module. Small amounts of powder were deposited onto the ATR crystal and the signal-to-noise ratio was increased by averaging 16 spectra. ATR correction was finally applied to all the spectra to correct the distorted shape of the spectra due to the increasing penetration depth with the wavelength.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) of glasses was recorded on a JEOL JEM 2100 electron microscope operating at 200 kV with a point resolution of 0.25 nm . The microscope is equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDXS) (INCA x-sight, Oxford

Instruments). The samples were prepared by dispersing small amounts of powder in EtOH and then a few drops of suspensions were deposited onto carbon-coated copper grids. The solvent was removed after drying the copper grids in air.

Raman spectra were obtained by a Raman Confocal microscope (InVia Reflex, Renishaw) using an excitation wavelength of 515 nm. The laser beam is focused on the sample with a 0.75×50 microscope objective. The laser power at the sample, the exposure time, and the number of accumulations for the Raman measurements correspond to 160 mW, 10 s and 20 respectively. The final spectra are the result of the merge of nine spectra, measured in groups of three in three different parts of the powder sample to check for possible structural inhomogeneities.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out using a Fisons MT500 spectrometer equipped with a hemispherical electron analyzer (CLAM2) and a non-monochromatic Mg K α (1253.6 eV) X-Ray source operated at 300 W. Spectra were collected at a pass energy of 20 eV, which is typical of high-resolution conditions and were analyzed using CasaXPS software (version 2.3.14). After a Shirley-type background subtraction, a curve fitting of the spectra was done using a combination of Lorentzian/Gaussian lines of variable proportions. The binding energy scale was calibrated using C 1s peak at 285 eV.

X-ray absorption (XAS) spectra at V K-edge were measured at the CLAES beamline at the ALBA synchrotron using a Si(111) double-crystal monochromator. The sample powders were pressed into pellets and placed at 45° to the incident beam and measured in fluorescence mode. The fluorescence signal was detected with a six-channel silicon drift detector placed at 90°. The energy calibration was obtained by measuring a V foil in transmission mode and the incident and transmitted signals were measured with two ionization chambers. Data analysis was performed using the ATHENA software [47].

2.3. Optical characterization

For optical characterization studies, glass samples were polished to achieve a uniform thickness of 13.0 mm.

Spectroscopic ellipsometry was performed using a Woollam VASE ellipsometer (Woollam Co. Inc.) set in photometry mode. The white light generated by an Xe lamp was filtered spectrally by a single monochromator, then collimated and directed through a polarizer to generate either s- or p-linear polarized light. The angles of incidence used for the measurements were 65, 70, and 75°.

UV–Vis–NIR absorbance spectra were acquired using a Varian Cary 5000 spectrophotometer within the wavelength range of 300–1000 nm, employing a step size of 1 nm. The absorption coefficient was obtained by considering the thickness of the samples.

For photoluminescence analysis, a Fluorolog 3 apparatus from Horiba was employed. Glass samples were subjected to irradiation by using a Xe lamp (450 W) as the excitation light source, with a slit width (bandpass) of 1 nm each, and the resulting emissions were detected using a PPD-900 detector from Horiba. The recorded spectra were meticulously corrected to account for both lamp emissions and detector responses. Fluorescence quantum yields (QY) were recorded using QuantaPhi-2 integrating sphere and Fluorolog-3 spectrofluorometer. The excitation was done at different excitation wavelengths (325 and 340 nm) and the emission was measured in the range of 380–800 nm. A neutral density filter was used to reduce the photon counts of the excitation beam.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Materials and elemental composition of the glasses

The prepared glasses were transparent and visual investigation showed that they are free of bubbles and other defects. After 2 h of annealing at 500 °C the transparent glasses were machined (cut and

polished) to obtain samples for optical characterization. Fig. S1 shows the XRD of the 0Bi, 1Bi, 2Bi, 4Bi, 6Bi, 2Bi-0.5V and 4Bi-0.5V glasses, confirming their amorphous glassy nature. TEM analysis was additionally conducted to further investigate the homogeneity of these samples and the absence of phase separation regions. Fig. S2 displays TEM micrographs and EDXS analysis of selected samples, revealing a uniform structure with no observable phase separation region. This observation aligns with the phase diagram of the SiO₂–B₂O₃–Na₂O system, indicating that the glass composition, as prepared, falls within the range of miscibility.

The chemical analysis of some glasses was performed and the results are resumed in Table S1. Considering the high number of glasses studied for this work, we limited the analysis to five compositions, undoped glass, 2Bi, 2Bi-0.5V, 4Bi, and 4Bi-0.5V doped glasses. The elemental composition analysis done by ICP-OES shows the presence of Si, B, Na, V, Bi, and Bi, without significant losses of the volatile components compared to the nominal composition, 35SiO₂–35B₂O₃–30Na₂O–xBi₂O₃–yV₂O₅. The biggest losses affect the Na₂O content that commonly occurs during the melt-quenching process. This loss increases with the addition of dopants such as Bi₂O₃, which acts as a network modifier, see next sections, and produces more NBO, thus decreasing the glass viscosity and the network connectivity.

3.2. DSC and thermal characterization

DSC curves of Bi-doped glasses in the range 425–550 °C are shown in Fig. 1a. The glass transition is associated with the endothermic process below 500 °C. As is seen from the inset of Fig. 1, the T_g values decrease linearly with the addition of Bi₂O₃. This behavior has been previously reported and it has been associated with the network modifier role of Bi³⁺ ions [45,48–50]. Fig. 1b shows the variation of T_g as a function of V₂O₅ content for a fixed content of Bi₂O₃ (4 mol%). The addition of V₂O₅ decreases further T_g, but the behavior is not linear when considering the glass without V₂O₅. After adding 0.05 and 0.1 mol% of V₂O₅, the T_g decreases by 3 and 6 °C, respectively, but only a small variation is observed at higher V₂O₅ content. V ions might act as glass former units, but further study will be necessary.

3.3. Structural characterization

Fig. 2a shows the FTIR spectra of Bi-doped glasses. There are no relevant vibrational bands beyond 1700 cm⁻¹ and thus the spectra are shown from 400 to 1700 cm⁻¹. All the spectra present similar vibrational bands and three main regions can be identified: (1) 1500–1200 cm⁻¹, (2) 1200–600 cm⁻¹, and (3) 600–400 cm⁻¹. The inset of Fig. 2a shows a detail of region (1) where a clear shift of this band towards lower energy is observed when increasing the Bi₂O₃ content. Similar behavior is observed in the region (2) around 1000 cm⁻¹ and the whole band also shifts towards lower energy with Bi₂O₃ addition. A deconvolution process was performed using Gaussian functions to identify individual vibrational bands. As it is known, the fit can converge using different combinations of Gaussian functions. To keep the analysis as simple as possible, we used the lower number of Gaussian functions that yielded a good agreement between data and fit. The FTIR spectrum of borosilicate glasses in this range has been previously described quite well with 9–10 vibrational bands [51]. The results of the fits are summarized in Table S2. Region (1) is described with three bands centered at around 1455, 1385, and 1319 cm⁻¹ that are associated with asymmetric stretching modes of [BO₃] units and BO₂O⁻ [51,52]. The intensity of the first and third bands decreases with Bi₂O₃ addition, instead, the intensity of the second band increases and shifts noticeably towards lower energy. This behavior can be associated with the formation of specific borate units with terminal NBO thanks to Bi₂O₃ addition that acts as a network modifier. Region (2) can be well described by four bands centered at around 1039, 927, 837, and 719 cm⁻¹ due to vibrations of [SiO₄] and [BO₄] tetrahedra [53]. The deconvolution of individual

Fig. 1. DTA curves of (a) 0Bi, 1Bi, 4Bi and 6Bi glasses and (b) $4\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 - x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.5$) glasses. The insets show the variation of T_g as a function of the Bi_2O_3 and V_2O_5 content. The error is $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and it is inside the symbol size in the inset of Fig. 1 (a). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. (a) FTIR spectra of 0Bi, 1Bi, 4Bi, and 6Bi glasses and (b) deconvolution of the spectra of 0Bi and 4Bi glasses. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

vibrations associated with $[\text{SiO}_4]$ and $[\text{BO}_4]$ is complicated due to the overlap of their vibrational bands. The silicate network is mainly composed of $[\text{SiO}_4]$ tetrahedra with a different number of bridging oxygens and indicated as Q^n (n denotes the number of bridging oxygens and $n = 4$ corresponds to a fully polymerized network). The first band is a combination of asymmetric vibrations of Si–O–Si bonds in $[\text{SiO}_4]$ tetrahedra (Q^3) and vibrations from $[\text{BO}_4]$ tetrahedra, especially from pentaborate groups [54,55]. The intensity of this band decreases when adding Bi_2O_3 . This can be explained considering that Bi_2O_3 is acting as a network modifier and produces more NBO, thus decreasing the network connectivity. The band around 927 cm^{-1} increases with Bi_2O_3 , and this vibration is associated with less polymerized $[\text{SiO}_4]$ tetrahedra (Q^2) as well as with vibrations of $[\text{BO}_4]$ tetrahedra in diborate groups [54]. The band at 837 cm^{-1} is associated with the stretching of B–O–B in $[\text{BO}_4]$ units from tri-, tetra-, and pentaborate groups, and its intensity decreases when the Bi_2O_3 content increases [56]. The characteristic absorption band at 806 cm^{-1} of the boroxol ring was not observed and its presence is ruled out or limited to a very low percentage [52]. The band at 719 cm^{-1} is assigned to bending vibrations of B–O–B linkage in the borate network and its intensity also decreases with Bi_2O_3 addition, further confirming the opening of the glass network when Bi_2O_3 is added to the glass. The last region (3) is formed by two bands at 532 and 459 cm^{-1} that are associated to Si–O–Si rocking motion and Si–O–Si bending vibrations [51,57]. No relevant changes are observed in this region with the addition of Bi_2O_3 . All these results indicate that the intensity of vibrational bands associated to a higher amount of NBO increases with Bi_2O_3 , confirming the modifier role of Bi^{3+} that produces a more open glass structure. Moreover, the variation in intensity and the decrease in

energy of vibrational bands associated to $[\text{BO}_3]$ units can be explained by considering the formation of specific borate groups.

Raman spectra of Bi-doped glasses and the deconvoluted bands are shown in Fig. 3a and b. The Raman spectra shown in Fig. 3 are the average of three spectra measured in different parts of the powder sample. The structural homogeneity of each sample is ensured by the similarity of the spectra measured in different parts of the sample, as shown in Fig. S3. There are remarkable differences in the spectra when adding Bi_2O_3 . From a general point of view, the spectra shift towards lower energy with Bi_2O_3 content. For Raman spectra, we define four main regions: (1) $300\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, (2) $600\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$, (3) $800\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and (4) $1250\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The results of the deconvolution process are summarized in Table S3. Region (1) is described by two main vibrations around 478 and 506 cm^{-1} . The band at 506 cm^{-1} is due to Si–O–Si bending and it shifts towards high energy and decreases in intensity with Bi_2O_3 addition. In previous reports, it has been observed a systematical shift of this band when introducing other modifier ions to the glass [58], and it has been also explained why this behavior is difficult to observe by FTIR compared to Raman. For the undoped glass, this is the main contribution observed at low energy, instead, an additional band around 478 cm^{-1} is observed for Bi-doped glasses and its intensity increases linearly with Bi_2O_3 content. This band is associated with Bi–O–Bi vibrations, but, some authors further deconvoluted this band in two individual Bi–O–Bi vibrations centered at 390 and 575 cm^{-1} [59], however, the average position of these two bands is consistent with our results. For the doped sample with the highest Bi content, there is an additional band at 352 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to the symmetric stretching of Bi–O–Bi in BiO_6 units [59]. Still, for the 6Bi sample, there is

Fig. 3. (a) Raman spectra of 0Bi, 1Bi, 4Bi, and 6Bi glasses and (b) deconvolution of the spectra of 0Bi and 4Bi. The inset of Figure (a) shows detail at low Raman shifts for the 6Bi glass. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

a tiny band observed around 145 cm^{-1} , as shown in the inset of Fig. 3a, which is associated to breathing mode of $[\text{BiO}_6]$ and $[\text{BiO}_3]$ units [59, 60]. This could be related to the presence of some Bi-clusters formed at high Bi contents. The bands observed in the region (2) are associated to B–O–Si stretching in borosilicate rings, symmetric breathing of metaborate rings, and symmetric stretching vibrations of $[\text{BO}_4]$ units in di- and tri-borate rings [61]. The last two bands decrease noticeably with Bi_2O_3 addition, suggesting the conversion of metaborate rings into other borate units. In the range $800\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, there are vibrations of both $[\text{SiO}_4]$ and $[\text{BO}_4]$ tetrahedra. Interestingly, for the 4Bi and 6Bi-doped samples two bands at 885 cm^{-1} can be associated to Bi–O vibration in $[\text{BiO}_3]$ units or to Si–O in $[\text{SiO}_4]$ tetrahedra with four NBO (Q^0). Similar to what was observed by FTIR, the vibrations associated to more polymerized $[\text{SiO}_4]$ units increase, confirming the higher depolymerization of the glass network upon Bi_2O_3 addition. Further, a band at around 1139 cm^{-1} is observed for the undoped glass and its intensity decreases to around 25 % for the 1Bi-doped sample and is not observed at a higher doping level. This band could be associated to residual $[\text{SiO}_4]$ units fully polymerized (Q^4) [60]. In region (4), the vibrations

associated to BO_3 units are observed and their behavior is similar to what was observed by FTIR, suggesting the conversion of different borate units with Bi_2O_3 addition.

3.4. Chemical characterization

XPS spectra of Bi 4f were measured to study the oxidation state of Bi. The general XPS spectrum is shown in Fig. S4 and the high-resolution XPS spectra of Bi 4f are shown in Fig. 4 together with their deconvolution. The results of the deconvolution are given in Table S4. The presence of Bi^{3+} is indicated by the peaks at 159.4 and 164.7 eV, corresponding to Bi 4f_{7/2} and 4f_{5/2} energy levels of Bi^{3+} , as observed for the Bi_2O_3 reference and in agreement with previous results [45]. The presence of two shoulders at 157.3 and 162.7 eV was associated with the presence of Bi^{2+} ions [62,63]. The formation of these reduced species could be related to 1) a partial decomposition of Bi_2O_3 occurring during the melting, 2) a stabilization of reduced Bi^{2+} species in the glass network at higher Bi contents, or 3) the reduction of Bi^{3+} upon intense X-rays excitation [63]. The last process is not excluded because even the

Fig. 4. High-resolution Bi 4f XPS spectra of Bi_2O_3 reference powder (a), 2Bi-doped glass and (c) 4Bi-doped glass. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

spectrum of Bi_2O_3 reference powder shows there are some reduced Bi species. Moreover, as will be shown later, the photoluminescence spectra change as a function of the Bi content and this is related to the stabilization of reduced Bi species in borosilicate glasses [64].

XAS characterization was performed at the V K-edge to study the oxidation state and local environment of V ions. As observed from XAS results, V is found in the form of four-coordinated V^{5+} , that is in the form of $[\text{VO}_4]^{3-}$ groups, see Fig. S5. These groups were also found in V_2O_5 -containing glasses [65,66]. Quite remarkably, the XAS spectra are practically the same for different V doping levels, indicating that V^{5+} ions in the glass are found in a very similar environment independent of the doping level, and this could be related to the low doping level used. Even though simulations have shown the presence of VO_4 , VO_5 and VO_6 units in vanadate glasses, with predominantly VO_5 , we can conclude according to XAS that in these glasses most of V is found in tetrahedral coordination but we do not discard the presence of minor penta- and octahedral units [67].

3.5. Optical characterization

Ellipsometry spectra of undoped and Bi-doped glasses were measured to obtain the refractive index and its dispersion relation, see Fig. S6 a. The ellipsometric data were fit with a Cauchy dispersion relation assuming $k = 0$. Fitting with a Sellmeier equation in the visible range yields similar results [68,69]. Fig. S6 b shows the refractive index at 588 nm as a function of Bi content, and the linear behavior is indicated by the good agreement between data and linear fit. Bi is the heaviest metal and a very dense element and the addition of 1 mol% of Bi_2O_3 increases the refractive index from 1.520 to 1.538, reaching up to reaching 1.603 for the sample with the highest Bi content, 6Bi-sample.

Fig. 5 shows the absorption coefficient resulting from the UV–Vis absorption spectroscopy measurements. It can be seen that all the prepared glasses show good transparency in the visible range (around 88 % for a thickness of 3 mm). It can be observed in Fig. 5 that the addition of Bi_2O_3 shifts the absorption edge towards longer wavelengths. The UV absorption edge of the glass is influenced by the polarizability of bonds and by the UV absorption bands of doping ions and impurities. A glass network with a higher amount of NBO increases the polarizability of Si–O and B–O bonds and, as a consequence, reduces the energy of the absorption edge. Moreover, the addition of doping ions may induce the

formation of UV absorption bands that overlap with the glass absorption edge and this may also contribute to shifting the absorption edge towards longer wavelengths. Therefore, the red shift observed in Fig. 5 is ascribed to two processes: 1) the presence of more polarizable bonds due to the formation of more NBO and 2) the overlap with the UV absorption band of Bi^{3+} ions. A similar behavior is observed when adding V_2O_5 for a fixed amount of Bi_2O_3 (4 mol%), see the inset of Fig. 5. At higher V_2O_5 concentrations (0.5 mol%), the glass presents a pale-yellow tone. No absorption bands around 450 nm are observed and the formation of Bi^0 species is thus excluded or below the detection limit.

The photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra of Bi-doped samples are shown in Fig. 6. The PLE spectra were obtained by measuring the blue emission of Bi^{3+} ions at 460 nm. The PLE spectra are very broad due to the $^1\text{S}_0\text{--}^3\text{P}_1$ transition of Bi^{3+} ions and agree with the results obtained previously for Bi-doped glasses [70]. The maxima of the spectra shift towards longer wavelengths when the Bi_2O_3 content increases. The maximum goes from 322 nm to 342 nm in an almost linear way when increasing the doping level from 0.5 to 4 mol% of Bi_2O_3 , see Fig. S7. For the 6Bi glass the emission is quenched, likely associated with the formation of Bi clusters as suggested by the Raman spectra. It has been reported a shift of the excitation spectra for Bi-doped oxide phosphors and the authors concluded that in their crystalline host, this behavior might be associated with the presence of different Bi centers that increase with the doping level [71]. Even though the highest PLE intensity was obtained for the 1Bi-doped glass, it should be considered that at the wavelength of interest of most commercial UV LEDs (340–380 nm), this sample presents a reduced emission while the 2Bi and 4Bi samples offer the highest PL intensity.

The PL spectra upon excitation at 340 and 355 nm are shown in Fig. 7. The spectra present an asymmetric shape due to the presence of several contributions probably associated with different Bi centers in the glass. The shape of the PL signal for the 0.5Bi, 1Bi, and 2Bi glasses is similar and the maximum of the emitted light is around 455 nm. Instead, for the 4Bi and 6Bi glasses, the PL spectra shift towards a longer wavelength, around 470 nm, and the emitted colors change from dark to lighter blue. By a deconvolution process, it was possible to see that the PL band is composed of at least three contributions at around 440, 480, and 580 nm. The spectral change observed when increasing the Bi content is associated with the increase of the orange-red emission at the expense of the blue emission, and the blue emission is also red-shifted, see Fig. S8 and Table S5. The origin of the blue emission in Bi-doped

Fig. 5. UV–Vis absorption spectra of 0Bi, 0.5Bi, 1Bi, 2Bi, 4Bi and 6Bi glasses. The inset shows the absorption spectra of the 4Bi-xV glasses ($x = 0, 0.1, 0.2$, and 0.5). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. PLE spectra of 0Bi, 0.5Bi, 1Bi, 2Bi, 4Bi, and 6Bi glasses obtained detecting the PL emission at 460 nm. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. PL emission spectra of 0.5Bi, 1Bi, 2Bi, 4Bi, and 6Bi glasses under excitation at a) 340 nm and b) 355 nm. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

glasses and phosphors has been typically associated with $^3P_1-^1S_0$ transitions, while the origin of the orange-red emission is still debated [72]. Some authors associated such emissions with Bi²⁺ centers [62,73] instead, other reports indicate that the emissions are Bi³⁺ ions in quite different local environments [31]. According to our XPS results, we can attribute this emission to Bi²⁺ species, as recently reported [64].

A glass doped with 0.5 mol% of V₂O₅ was also studied for reference to check the emission of vanadium ions in the glass. The PLE excitation, shown in Fig. 8a, consists of a broad band with a maximum at 330 nm and a shoulder at around 360 nm. Very similar results were reported by other authors for aluminosilicate glasses doped with V⁵⁺ [74]. V⁵⁺ ions have a d⁰ electronic configuration and no emission from d levels is possible. Instead, this PLE band is associated with the charge transfer (CT) from O²⁻ to V⁵⁺ in tetrahedral coordination with the transitory formation of V⁴⁺ and O⁻ ions [74,75]. The CT process from these excited V⁴⁺ ions to O⁻ produces again oxidized V⁵⁺ ions and a consequent bright yellow luminescence centered around 580 nm, see Fig. 7b. The PL spectra after excitation at 340–365 nm are very similar and the main variation is in their intensity which decreases when increasing the excitation wavelength, in agreement with the PLE spectrum. This intense and broad emission, with an FWHM of about 220 nm, is extremely appealing for yellow-emitting phosphors, and in combination with blue-emitting ions, it is promising to produce white light emission.

The PLE spectra of Bi–V codoped glasses are shown in Fig. 9. The emitted intensity at 460 nm (Bi³⁺) decreases with V addition and it also suffers important spectral changes. The reasons behind this decrease in intensity is associated to several reasons: 1) the glass absorption edge shifts toward longer wavelengths when increasing the V content (see Fig. 5), so part of the UV photons are absorbed by the glass matrix; 2) V ions also absorb in this spectral region which reduce the photons available to excite Bi ions; 3) there is an energy transfer (ET) band from Bi³⁺ to V⁵⁺ at around 350 nm that contributes both to the intensity decrease as well as to the spectral change [76]. Another possibility behind this decrease in intensity could be a higher stabilization of Bi²⁺

species as V content increases. However, according to XPS results, this is not the case, because the Bi²⁺/Bi³⁺ ratio is very similar in glasses doped with 0.1 (35 %) and 0.5 (32 %) mol% of V₂O₅.

The PLE spectra obtained detecting the emission at 570 nm (V⁵⁺) are shown in Fig. S9. The obtained results indicate that no relevant changes are observed when increasing the V content for a fixed Bi content. Hence the position of the yellow emission of V⁵⁺ ions at 570 nm seems almost independent of the V content and most of it could be attributed to the ET from Bi³⁺ to V⁵⁺. At the same time, considering that the Bi content is the same, the incorporation of V as a codopant, results in a reduction of the Bi emission at 460 nm together with a shift of the maximum at 570 nm associated with the V⁵⁺, after excitation at 340 nm that corresponds to the maximum of the excitation spectra of Bi and V codoped borosilicate glasses, see Fig. 9. This reduction together with the shift suggests that the Bi³⁺ relaxes non-radiatively by ET to V⁵⁺.

The PL spectra of glasses doped with 2 and 4 mol% of Bi₂O₃ and codoped with 0.05 mol% of V₂O₅ and excited at different excitation wavelengths are shown in Fig. 10 together with the corresponding CIE diagrams. The samples were excited in the 340–365 nm range by increasing the excitation wavelength in steps of 5 nm. The PL emission shows a broad spectrum due to the overlap of Bi³⁺ and V⁵⁺ emissions and the corresponding emitted color in the CIE diagram shows that near white light emission is achieved for the 4Bi-0.05V sample. Table 1 summarizes the corresponding color-correlated temperatures and indicates how a tuning of the emitted color is possible by changing the doping level and the excitation wavelength. As the excitation wavelength increases, there is an increase of the yellow-orange emission of V⁵⁺ and this shifts the emitted light towards a warmer color. For a fixed excitation wavelength (355 nm) the emitted color shifts from warm white toward yellow when increasing the V content, see Fig. S10. A similar behavior is observed for other excitation wavelengths. Figs. S11 and S12 show the PL spectra for 2Bi and 4Bi glasses codoped with higher amounts of V₂O₅ where a clear predominance of yellow emission is observed.

Fig. 8. a) PLE of 0.5V-doped samples obtained detecting the emission at 570 nm. b) PL spectra for different excitation wavelengths in the range 340–365 nm. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. a) PLE of a) 2Bi-xV and b) 4Bi-xV ($x = 0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2,$ and 0.5) obtained by detecting the PL emission at 460 nm. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. PL emission of a) 2Bi-0.05V and c) 4Bi-0.05V doped samples excited in the 340–365 nm range. b), d) Corresponding CIE diagrams with the Planckian locus. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 1

Correlated color temperature for 2Bi- and 4Bi-doped glasses codoped with 0.05V.

λ_{exc} (nm)	2Bi-0.05V	4Bi-0.05V
	CCT (K)	CCT (K)
340	4919	6135
345	4670	5811
350	4461	5545
355	4140	5343
360	4047	5155
365	4010	4983

QY of certain glass samples were assessed to quantitatively analyze the luminescence of the glasses and the impact of increasing dopant content. The 2Bi-0.05V sample exhibited a quantum yield (QY) of 11.9 % and 8.0 % upon 325 nm and 340 nm excitation, respectively. However, this value decreased to approximately 4 % when the V content increased to 0.5 mol%, as shown in Table S6. This phenomenon may be attributed to higher absorption by the glass matrix as the V content increases (UV edge shifting towards longer wavelengths), as well as potential inefficiencies in energy transfer processes between Bi and V. These findings align with the observed lower photoluminescence (PL) and photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra as the V content increases. A possible strategy to increase the QY could be the use of a different glass matrix to shift the PLE curve of the Bi ions towards longer wavelengths, thus better matching the UV excitation range with UV LEDs, and also decreasing the UV absorption of the glass itself.

4. Conclusions

Transparent borosilicate glasses codoped with Bi and V were prepared by melt-quenching at a relatively low temperature, and they show broadband emission in the Vis. The analysis of the results shows that Bi ions are mostly present as Bi^{3+} and act as network modifiers, producing depolymerization of the glass network with a consequent linear decrease of the glass transition temperature as a function of the Bi content. Instead, V^{5+} ions are found in tetrahedral coordination to form VO_4 units. The PL emission of Bi ions upon UV excitation is in the spectral blue region, related to Bi^{3+} , and broadens and shifts towards longer wavelengths as the Bi content increases, likely related to the presence of Bi^{3+} in the different local environment as well as the stabilization of reduced Bi^{2+} species. The V-doped glasses show a broad yellow emission from V^{5+} that comes from a charge transfer process between temporally formed O^- and V^{4+} ions after absorption of UV photons. The combination of the Bi and V ions light emission produces a broadband emission covering the whole visible spectrum. From the analysis of the PL and PLE spectra energy transfer processes between the Bi and V ions are identified. White light emission is obtained by varying the doping level and the excitation wavelength, allowing a correlated color temperature spanning from 6135 to 4010 K to be achieved. The sample doped with 2Bi and codoped with 0.05V showed a QY of 11.9 % and 8.0 % for excitation at 325 and 340 nm, respectively. These results show an interesting combination of inexpensive elements to produce broadband emission with application in UV-WLED.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

G.G designed and carried out experiments and performed data analysis. C. Pérez prepared the materials and performed experiments and data analysis. B. Wolfrum and J.J. Velázquez performed optical characterization (PL, PLE and QY) and data analysis. H. Kaňková performed ICP-OES measurements and data analysis. I. Llorent performed XPS experiments and data analysis. I. Muñoz Ochando performed Raman characterization. R. Serna and J. Gonzalo supervised the data analysis and interpretation and obtained funding. All the authors

discussed the results and wrote and revised the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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